

Widespread underestimation of others' pro-environmental attitudes in a diverse sample of European stakeholders

Die unterschätzte Umweltorientierung anderer: Evidenz aus einer heterogenen europäischen Stakeholder-Stichprobe

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Author statement

BK: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Writing – original draft & reviewing and editing. A-MN: Methodology, Project administration, Writing – reviewing and editing. YJ, DI, AY: Methodology, Writing – reviewing and editing. JE, RK: Project administration, Writing – reviewing and editing. PB, DH, BJK, FM, MP, VS, FZ: Investigation, Writing – reviewing and editing. This study was funded by the EU Horizon grant PRO-COAST (Project ID 101082327) and additional support from UK Research and Innovation for the same project (grant number 10115053). Conflicts of interest: none.

Abstract

Environmental pluralistic ignorance – the finding that people often severely underestimate the pro-environmental attitudes of others – has been referred to as a “false social reality”. This is important because personal attitudes are influenced by the perceived attitudes of others. This study extends prior findings of pluralistic ignorance, and correlations between personal and perceived attitudes, in a sample ($n = 337$) combining stakeholders from eight local environmental case studies across Europe (Estonia, Ireland, Italy, Malta, Norway, Romania, Slovenia, UK). For example, while 53% of participants reported being willing to accept cuts in their standard of living to protect the environment, their mean estimate was that 30% would be willing to do so. Pluralistic ignorance for willingness to sacrifice, and for environmentalist self-identity, is predicted in 80% and 87% respectively of other similar case studies (95% confidence interval lower bounds 58% and 61% respectively). The correlation between personal and perceived attitudes is consistent across contexts for willingness to sacrifice, but possibly not for environmentalist self-identity. The findings support an approach to local interventions for environmental change where opinion surveying is conducted early and results used as part of education for change, rather than the typical educate-then-survey approach.

Keywords

Environmental pluralistic ignorance, local stakeholders, social norms, willingness to sacrifice, environmentalist self-identity

Impact statement

We found that stakeholders in local environmental projects across Europe consistently underestimate others' environmentally friendly attitudes – for example, although most participants (53%) were willing to sacrifice their standard of living to protect the environment, the average guess was that only 30% would be willing. This kind of inaccurate belief is common – globally, most people tend to have attitudes in favour of action on the environment but also believe that most other people are much less keen, which has been called living in a “false social reality”. This is known to inhibit action on the environment, but it's also known to be hard to change this. We recommend that those working with stakeholder groups survey and share results early – attitudes are often more positive than expected, and making this visible may prevent the false social reality from taking hold.

76 Zusammenfassung

77 Umweltbezogene pluralistische Ignoranz – also die Erkenntnis, dass Menschen die
78 umweltfreundlichen Einstellungen anderer oft stark unterschätzen – wird auch als
79 „falsche soziale Realität“ bezeichnet. Das ist deshalb von Bedeutung, weil persön-
80 liche Einstellungen durch die wahrgenommenen Einstellungen anderer beein-
81 flusst werden. Diese Studie erweitert frühere Befunde zur pluralistischen Ignoranz
82 sowie zum Zusammenhang von persönlichen und wahrgenommenen Einstellun-
83 gen anhand einer Stichprobe (n = 337), die Akteur*innen aus acht lokalen umwelt-
84 bezogenen Fallstudien in Europa vereint (Estland, Irland, Italien, Malta, Norwe-
85 gen, Rumänien, Slowenien, Vereinigtes Königreich). Dabei gaben beispielsweise
86 53 % der Teilnehmenden an, bereit zu sein, Einschnitte in ihrem Lebensstandard
87 zum Schutz der Umwelt hinzunehmen, während ihre durchschnittliche Schät-
88 zung war, dass andere lediglich zu 30 % dazu bereit wären. Pluralistische Ignoranz
89 in Bezug auf die Bereitschaft zu persönlichen Opfern sowie auf die umweltbezo-
90 gene Selbstidentität wird in 80 % bzw. 87 % vergleichbarer Fallstudien vorhergesagt
91 (untere Grenze des 95 %-Konfidenzintervalls: 58 % bzw. 61 %). Der Zusammen-
92 hang zwischen persönlichen und wahrgenommenen Einstellungen ist kontext-
93 übergreifend konsistent für die Bereitschaft zu persönlichen Opfern, möglicher-
94 weise jedoch nicht für die umweltbezogene Selbstidentität. Die Ergebnisse unter-
95 stützen einen Ansatz für lokale Interventionen zum Umweltwandel, bei dem Mei-
96 nungsbefragungen frühzeitig durchgeführt und die Ergebnisse als Teil der Bil-
97 dungsarbeit für Veränderung genutzt werden – im Gegensatz zum üblichen An-
98 satz „erst aufklären, dann befragen“.

99 Schlüsselwörter

100 Umweltbezogene pluralistische Ignoranz, lokale Akteur*innen, soziale Normen,
101 Bereitschaft zu persönlichen Opfern, umweltbezogene Selbstidentität

102 Impact-Statement

103 Wir haben festgestellt, dass Akteur*innen in lokalen Umweltprojekten in ganz Eu-
104 ropa die umweltfreundlichen Einstellungen anderer systematisch unterschätzen.
105 So war beispielsweise die Mehrheit der Teilnehmenden (53 %) bereit, ihren Le-
106 bensstandard zum Schutz der Umwelt zu senken, während die durchschnittliche
107 Annahme war, dass nur 30 % dazu bereit wären. Diese Art von Fehlwahrnehmung
108 ist weit verbreitet: Weltweit vertreten die meisten Menschen Einstellungen, die
109 Umweltmaßnahmen befürworten, glauben jedoch gleichzeitig, dass die Mehrheit
110 der Anderen deutlich weniger engagiert ist – ein Zustand, der als Leben in einer
111 „falschen sozialen Realität“ beschrieben wird. Es ist bekannt, dass diese falsche
112 Wahrnehmung Umweltengagement hemmt, zugleich aber schwer zu verändern
113 ist. Wir empfehlen daher, dass Personen, die mit Stakeholder-Gruppen arbeiten,
114 frühzeitig Einstellungen erheben und die Ergebnisse transparent teilen. Die Ein-
115 stellungen sind häufig positiver als erwartet, und ihre Sichtbarmachung kann ver-
116 hindern, dass sich eine falsche soziale Realität verfestigt.

1 Introduction

Sparkman et al. (2022) found that “Americans experience a false social reality by underestimating popular climate policy support by nearly half”. This represents an example of pluralistic ignorance – when individuals’ perceptions of others’ attitudes are systematically inaccurate (Miller, 2023). Pluralistic ignorance on environmental issues is globally widespread, with large cross-national surveys showing systematic underestimation of public support for climate policies and climate concern (Andre et al., 2024; Geiger, Köhler, et al., 2025). One explanation is that mainstream and social media representations are often perceived as more representative than they in fact are (Miller, 2023). Media exaggerates environmental controversy, because controversy attracts attention (Bray, 2018), because of vested interests (Adame et al., 2025; Coan et al., 2021), and because of a desire to appear “balanced” (Boykoff & Boykoff, 2004).

In a recent review of environmental pluralistic ignorance, Geiger, Imada, et al. (2025) found that most studies focused on the general public, rather than specific groups within societies. Most studies focusing on specific groups targeted those with broad political affiliations or demographic traits. Some studies that target more local groups do exist and provide important insights. For example, recreational fishers in Eastern Cape, South Africa, overestimate regulation non-compliance amongst their peers, and those most prone to such overestimation are most prone themselves to non-compliance (Bova et al., 2017). However, Geiger, Imada, et al. (2025) found no studies investigating pluralistic ignorance within a broad variety of specific local groups.

This is an important gap because there are reasons why pluralistic ignorance might be amplified or attenuated when the reference group is narrower and closer to the individual. On the one hand, more frequent within-group contact might lead to more accurate perceptions of within-group attitudes (Shelton & Richeson, 2005). On the other hand, when outward (non-)expression of attitudes is determined in part by conformity to inaccurately perceived norms, greater within-group contact can reinforce a self-perpetuating spiral of silence or support for privately-dissented-from norms (Bicchieri, 2006; Geiger & Swim, 2016; Geiger, Imada, et al., 2025).

We therefore present a confirmatory analysis of pluralistic ignorance in a heterogeneous sample of stakeholders in different local environmental situations across Europe. Preregistered analyses test the hypotheses that for each of two relevant constructs, the proportion of participants who agree with a relevant item will be greater than the proportion that participants estimate to agree.¹ Because our sample is diverse, featuring data from six categories of environmental issue stakeholders from case studies in eight countries, we also explore the generality of this effect using random models.

Related to pluralistic ignorance is the observation that individuals’ personal attitudes tend to be correlated with their perceptions of others’ related attitudes (Capuano & Chekroun, 2024). This is also common in environmental contexts

¹ We also preregistered an equivalent hypothesis but for disagreement rather than agreement, which was also confirmed (see Supplementary Materials).

(e.g., Chen et al., 2022; Poortinga, 2025) – e.g., farmers beliefs about others' typical sustainability practices predict personal uptake (Swart et al., 2023). Such correlations tend to be referred to as false consensus (Steiner et al., 2025), or as social influence (Capuano & Chekroun, 2024), depending on which causal direction is emphasised. We therefore also engage in confirmatory analysis of this correlation, as both causal directions can play a role in reducing pro-environmental action (Geiger, Imada, et al., 2025). Preregistered analyses test a hypothesis for each of two constructs: agreement with a relevant item will be associated with the proportion of others that participants estimate to agree. Again, we explore the generality of this effect using random models.

We focus on two attitude constructs – environmentalist self-identity (ESI) and willingness to sacrifice for the environment (WTS) – both of which are important for environmentally relevant behaviour (Davis et al., 2011; Lange et al., 2018). Because ESI is considered a cause of WTS (Davis et al., 2011), and because perceived norms are considered a cause of personal attitudes, we also explore a comparison of the extent to which WTS is independently predicted by ESI and perceived WTS norms. The work is intended to inform those working with local environmental situations in Europe as to the likelihood that their stakeholders are subject to pluralistic ignorance in these constructs, and the extent to which attitudes are related to (and thus potentially determined by) perceived norms.

2 Methods

2.1 Participants and study background

Questions were added opportunistically to surveys primarily intended to inform practice within the case studies of the PRO-COAST project, a research program directly supporting ecological improvements in local coastal communities across nine European countries (PRO-COAST, 2024). Participants were recruited and questionnaire translations implemented by local partners, targeting convenience samples of specific local stakeholder groups. Some partners autonomously made changes when translating and implementing, causing some (or, for one case study, all) currently relevant data to be missing. Missingness is the only exclusion criterion.

Across the eight includable case studies there were responses from 453 participants, with 337 includable in at least one current analysis, 319 in ESI analyses, and 218 in WTS analyses. Includable participants came from 32 local stakeholder groups, with 65% having university degrees, 50% identifying as women, 49% as men, and 1% as non-binary, 28% were 18 to 30 years old, 28% 31 to 50, 21% 51 to 70, and 11% 71 or older. The mean self-reported economic situation on a five-point scale from Bad (1) to Good (5) was 3.75.

Sample size was determined by asking local partners to obtain as much data as possible by a given date. Stakeholder groups were combined into the following cross-case-study stakeholder categories: commercial ($n = 31$), environment protectors (43), government (29), local community (137), tourists (99), and (non-commercial) wild resource users (79).

We include multiple case studies and stakeholder categories not because of relevant comparison hypotheses but to test the generality of our hypotheses, and we model

group variables to that end – stakeholder category as fixed, and case study as random. Stakeholder categories are relatively comprehensive, rather than being a sample from a population. Case study is appropriately considered as a random factor because although case selection was not random, cases are representative of the large population of European localities with environmental issues.

2.2 Measures

We use a pair of Likert agree-disagree items to assess each of our focal constructs. The ESI item pair is from a commonly used set of three (e.g., van der Werff et al., 2013): “Acting environmentally friendly is an important part of who I am” and “I see myself as an environmentally friendly person”. The WTS item pair is from a commonly used set of four (e.g., Vicente et al., 2021), originally from the International Social Survey Programme (International Social Survey Programme, 2010): “I would be willing to accept cuts in my standard of living to protect the environment” and “I would be willing to pay much higher taxes in order to protect the environment”.

The paired items allow reliability assessment (ESI: $r = .64$; WTS: $r = .66$) but we henceforth focus on single items, because comparisons of perceived and actual norms require single items. For assessment of perceived norms, participants were asked: “Please think about the way you were invited to this survey, and about other members of [specified own stakeholder group] who would also agree to answer the survey when invited. Imagine ten of those people answering the survey. How many of those ten do you guess would agree with the following statements?” They answered concerning the first item from each of the above ESI and WTS pairs.

Additional descriptions of the sample and data collection and analysis methods are available in Supplementary Materials.

3 Results

3.1 Pluralistic ignorance

The grand mean percentage (across cross studies) of participants who agreed with the ESI item (“Acting environmentally friendly is an important part of who I am”) was 87%, whereas the grand mean percentage that participants guessed would agree was 59%. For the WTS item (“I would be willing to accept cuts in my standard of living to protect the environment”), 53% agreed, whereas the percentage they guessed would agree was 30%. Figure 1 displays this data broken down by case study and stakeholder category.

240 **Figure 1**
 241 *Pluralistic ignorance for ESI and WTS across case studies and stakeholder categories*

242
 243 *Note.* Pluralistic ignorance is indicated when the percentage of participants who agree with items is greater than the percentage they guess agree
 244 (below the diagonal line). Sample size illustrations are a rough guide (exact values are in Supplementary Tables S2 and S3). Some groups are
 245 very small, for example because a given area may have few representatives of local government available to survey. Groups with $n < 3$ are omitted
 246 from the figure.

247 For each construct we calculated a pluralistic ignorance score for each participant
 248 as the percentage of those they estimate to agree with the relevant item, minus the
 249 actual percentage for their stakeholder group. Mean scores were positive for both
 250 constructs, confirming pluralistic ignorance, both p -values $< .001$, permutation
 251 sign test with 99,999 samples (Oehlert, 2023).

252 As an exploratory extension to the above preregistered confirmatory analysis, we
 253 examined the predicted generality of these results across the population of case
 254 studies represented by our sample. We modelled each construct's pluralistic igno-
 255 rance score as a function of stakeholder category and case study, creating paramet-
 256 rically bootstrapped confidence intervals (99,999 samples) for the proportion of

257 case studies in the population estimated to have positive mean pluralistic igno-
258 rance scores. For ESI, the estimated population proportion of case studies showing
259 pluralistic ignorance, with 95% CI, is 80%, [58%, 97%], and for WTS, 88%, [61%,
260 100%] (note this assumes the same distributions of stakeholder categories as in our
261 sample).

262 **3.2 Correlations between perceived norms and personal** 263 **attitude**

264 Using ordinal regressions, we model personal attitude as a function of perceived
265 attitude norms, progressively adding additional contextual variables: stakeholder
266 category (fixed), then case study (random), then the interaction between perceived
267 norms and either stakeholder category or case study (Table 1). Model types 1 to 3
268 are (with one exception²) as preregistered, Model types 4 and 5 are exploratory.

269 Across our range of contextual control models, there are consistent relationships
270 between perceived norms and personal attitudes for both ESI and WTS (Table 1).
271 A single exception is that when allowing the association of perceived norms with
272 ESI to vary by case study (ESI Model 4), the association becomes non-significant,
273 suggesting that this effect may be more case-study-dependent. However, the addi-
274 tion of the interaction did not improve the quality of the model (compare AIC-
275 values for ESI Models 3 and 4 in Table 1), so this could also represent a power
276 issue. Further comparisons of AIC values in Table 1 (noting that a reduction in
277 AIC of at least 2 is generally regarded as a meaningful improvement, Burnham &
278 Anderson, 2002) indicate clear main effects of stakeholder category and case study
279 on ESI, but not WTS.

² We preregistered to conduct beta regressions if there were violations of the proportional odds assumption of ordinal regression. As there was a violation, we conducted beta regressions, producing in essence the same results (see Supplementary Materials).

Table 1*Ordinal regression models predicting individual personal attitude (ESI or WTS) as a function of perceived norms*

Model	Contextual control variables	ESI			WTS		
		OR [95% CI]	<i>p</i>	AIC	OR [95% CI]	<i>p</i>	AIC
1	None	1.36 [1.08, 1.71]	.008	647.5	1.80 [1.40, 2.33]	<.001	632.6
2	stakeholder category	1.40 [1.10, 1.78]	.007	637.8	1.82 [1.40, 2.40]	<.001	638.1
3	stakeholder category + case study	1.42 [1.09, 1.85]	.009	615.8	1.79 [1.36, 2.36]	<.001	638.7
4	stakeholder category + case study + perceived norms * case study	1.39 [0.93, 2.08]	.114	623.6	1.75 [1.12, 2.75]	.015	642.0
5	stakeholder category + case study + perceived norms * stakeholder category	1.42 [1.02, 1.99]	.040	617.2	1.79 [1.36, 2.36]	<.001	640.7

Note. OR = odds ratio. AIC = Akaike information criterion. The perceived norm predictor is standardised.

280 Finally, we explored the relative predictive power of ESI and perceived WTS
 281 norms to explain WTS, by extending WTS model 3 by adding personal ESI as a
 282 predictor. The resulting model indicates very similar predictive power for both
 283 personal ESI, OR [95% CI] = 1.81 [1.40, 2.33], $p < 0.001$, and perceived WTS norms,
 284 OR [95% CI] = 1.75 [1.33, 2.31], $p < 0.001$.

285 4 Discussion

286 The results confirm pluralistic ignorance in two potentially important constructs,
 287 willingness to sacrifice for the environment (WTS) and environmentalist self-identity
 288 (ESI), in a diverse sample of environmental stakeholders from case studies
 289 across Europe. The levels of misperception were appreciable, with guessed agree-
 290 ment roughly two-thirds of actual agreement, approaching the level of disconnect
 291 sometimes described as a “false social reality” (Sparkman et al., 2022). For WTS,
 292 the inhibiting effects on pro-environmental behaviour of this underestimation
 293 (Chen et al., 2022; Geiger & Swim, 2016; Geiger, Imada, et al., 2025) may be
 294 marked, because although a narrow majority (53%) of stakeholders stated a will-
 295 ingness to sacrifice, the average guess was only 30%.

296 The broadness of our sample supports predictions about the how widespread plu-
 297 ralistic ignorance would be across the population of which these case studies are
 298 representative. For these constructs, pluralistic ignorance is estimated to be ob-
 299 served in around 80% to 90% of case studies, and 95% CIs indicate true proportions
 300 are unlikely to be less than around 60%.

301 We also confirmed the well-known relationship between perceived norms and per-
 302 sonal attitudes. The effect sizes were appreciable – odds ratios of 1.4 and 1.8 for
 303 ESI and WTS respectively indicate that a one standard deviation increase in per-

304 ceived norms is associated with a 40% or 80% increase in the odds of a higher re-
305 sponse. Perceived norms about WTS predicted WTS as strongly as ESI did. This
306 is in line with previous evidence, for example showing that perceived ingroup
307 norms can be amongst the strongest predictors of pro-environmental attitudes
308 (Cole et al., 2022).

309 The broadness of our sample also enabled models of contextual variation in this
310 relationship, potentially supporting generalised claims. Modelling did indeed indi-
311 cate such a strongly general effect for WTS, although such conclusions are not
312 merited for ESI, where results were compatible with either a lack of strong gener-
313 ality or a lack of power to detect it.

314 A key study limitation is the lack of information about norms directly related to
315 the focal environmental situations of the local case studies. Implementers of local
316 environmental solutions would benefit from knowing about directly relevant atti-
317 tudes. One case study (Arne, UK) does have relevant data from an additional sur-
318 vey, which we summarise here as an illustrative example of potential future work
319 (see Supplemental Material for details). There is a proposal to cull invasive grey
320 squirrels to allow reestablishment of native red squirrels, and we observed both
321 pluralistic ignorance (82% support, estimated as 51%) and a correlation between
322 perceived norms and own attitudes regarding this proposal.

323 Turning to the broader implications of our results, we note that unfortunately,
324 communicating real norms to dispel pluralistic ignorance is not a panacea. For ex-
325 ample, although much evidence initially suggested that this can effectively change
326 behaviour in health contexts (Sheeran et al., 2016), later meta-analysis indicated
327 this effect was due to publication bias (Papakonstantinou et al., 2025). Further,
328 attempts to dispel pluralistic ignorance in environmental contexts have not been
329 shown to have appreciable effects (Geiger, Köhler, et al., 2025; Vlasceanu et al.,
330 2024). We also note a relevant personal observation – sometimes those promoting
331 local environmental change are not keen to survey opinion about issues they view
332 as controversial until they feel they have sufficiently educated the public. This may
333 relate to observations that key decision makers themselves often underestimate
334 public support for environmental measures (Faleide & Nordø, 2025; Tanase et al.,
335 2025).

336 Together, our data and these observations lead to a key recommendation – norms
337 should be communicated early, before pluralistic ignorance is able to establish it-
338 self. The public can usually be expected to be supportive of environmental initia-
339 tives, but typical discourse can be expected to create pluralistic ignorance with neg-
340 ative effects, which once established are difficult to shift. Therefore, those propos-
341 ing environmental initiatives, for which perceptions of support may be initially
342 uncertain, should survey representative samples early and be prepared to use re-
343 sults as part of education, rather than educating then surveying. This is somewhat
344 at odds with common practice, emphasising an information-first approach (e.g.,
345 European Commission, n.d.), but aligns with recommendations that active partic-
346 ipation from stakeholders should be as early as possible (Reed, 2008).

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5 Open science statement

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The analysis methods and hypotheses are, except where otherwise noted, as per a preregistration (Anon, 2025a). All deviations are noted in the main text and detailed in Supplementary Material. All exploratory (non-preregistered) analysis is labelled as such. We confirm that we have reported all measures, conditions, data exclusions, and how we determined our sample sizes. We have pre-registered additional hypotheses concerning the broader PRO-COAST stakeholder survey data set from which the current variables are derived (Anon, 2025b, 2025c), but none of these hypotheses concern perception of norms.

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All data and analysis scripts (including R Markdown showing results) can be downloaded from our GitHub repository (Anon, 2026) which will be preserved with a snapshot on Zenodo following acceptance of the manuscript.

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467 unavailable,
468 [https://web.archive.org/web/20250905235257/https://pro-](https://web.archive.org/web/20250905235257/https://pro-coast.sycl.net/10/pro-coast-case-studies)
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1 **Supplementary Material for manuscript:**
2 **Widespread underestimation of others' pro-environmental atti-**
3 **tudes in a diverse sample of European stakeholders**

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1 Method details

1.1 Sample description

Table S1 specifies the eight included case studies, responsible PRO-COAST partners, the stakeholder groups they recruited (with sample sizes), the broader stakeholder categories those groups were assigned to, and the methods used for recruitment. Information about each of the focal environmental situations faced by stakeholders is available at the PRO-COAST website (PRO-COAST, 2024).

Table S1

Case studies, partners, data collection methods, stakeholder groups and categories, and sample sizes thereof

Case study	Partner	Stakeholder category	Stakeholder group	Data collection methods	n (n_{ESI} , n_{WTS})
Kloogaranna, Estonia	Tallinn University of Technology	Environment protectors	National nature conservation institutions	Conducted online, shared via organisations in the partner's network, and at events organised by the partner	2 (2, 2)
		Government	Local government		2 (2, 0)
		Local community	Local (permanent) community representatives		10 (10, 0)
<i>Case study subtotal</i>					14 (14, 2)
Streedagh, Ireland	Atlantic Technological University	Commercial	Farmers / landowners	Conducted online, recruitment via emails to stakeholders and QR codes displayed at the beach	6 (6, 6)
		Environment protectors	NGO National Park & Wildlife Services		1 (1, 1) 1 (1, 1)
		Government	Sligo County Council		6 (6, 6)
<i>Case study subtotal</i>					14 (14, 14)
Frigole, Italy	University of Salento	Environment protectors	NGO	Paper questionnaires, shared via organisations in the partner's network, and at events they organised	7 (7, 0)
		Government	Local government		1 (1, 0)
		Local community	Higher education Local citizens		16 (16, 0) 10 (10, 0)
<i>Case study subtotal</i>					34 (34, 0)
Comino, Malta	Friends of the Earth Malta	Commercial	Tour operator, boat operator	Recruitment via partner's networks	6 (6, 6)
		Government	Environment Ministry & relevant managing authorities		11 (11, 10)

			Malta Tourism Authority ministry		3 (3, 3)
			Ministry of Gozo & local council		1 (1, 1)
		Tourists	Local visitors / foreign tourists	Recruitment through QR codes displayed to tourists, and additionally through a magazine advertisement	73 (73, 72)
		<i>Case study subtotal</i>			94 (94, 92)
Bergen, Norway	University of Bergen	Environment protectors	Divers and others who clean up underwater	Recruitment via email to partner's networks, complemented by paid and organic social media posts	15 (15, 15)
			Environmental organisations		5 (5, 5)
			Possible financiers for cleanup operations		1 (1, 1)
		Government	Directorate of Fisheries		1 (1, 1)
		Wild resource users	Fishers		31 (30, 31)
		<i>Case study subtotal</i>			53 (52, 53)
Corbu, Romania	Total PR	Commercial	Small business owners	Conducted online, shared with existing networks and collaborators of the partner	1 (0, 1)
		Government	Local authorities		3 (0, 3)
		Tourists	Tourists		12 (0, 12)
		<i>Case study subtotal</i>			16 (0, 16)
Strunjan, Slovenia	University of Primorska	Commercial	Farmers	Distributed online to stakeholders the partner regularly collaborates with	9 (9, 0)
		Environment protectors	Protected area practitioners		3 (3, 0)
		Local community	Local community		59 (59, 0)
		<i>Case study subtotal</i>			71 (71, 0)
Arne, UK	Anatrack Ltd	Commercial	Farmers / Foresters	Leaflet inviting to online survey distributed door-to-door throughout the parish	2 (2, 2)
		Environment protectors	Nature conservation professional		3 (3, 3)
		Local community	Community member		16 (15, 16)
			Hunters / Fishers		3 (3, 3)

	Wild resource users	Recreational wildlife user	17 (17, 17)
	<i>Case study subtotal</i>		41 (40, 41)
<i>Stakeholder category subtotals</i>	Commercial		24 (23, 15)
	Environment protectors		38 (38, 28)
	Government		28 (25, 24)
	Local community		111 (110, 16)
	Tourists		85 (73, 84)
	Wild resource users		51 (50, 51)
<i>Grand totals</i>			337 (319, 218)

Note. Sample sizes are any includable cases, and in parentheses, complete cases for ESI then complete cases for WTS.

1.2 Questionnaire items

Questionnaires contained additional items not mentioned here, to be included in future reports from the PRO-COAST consortium. The items used to measure willingness to sacrifice (WTS) and environmental self-identify (ESI), and perceived norms for WTS and ESI agreement, are stated in the main text. The response scale for the items used to measure WTS and ESI was five-point: “Disagree” (1), “Slightly disagree” (2), “Neither disagree nor agree” (3), “Slightly agree” (4), and “Agree” (5). The items used to measure perceived norms for disagreement were the same as those for agreement, with the word disagree substituted for agree. Response scales for perceived norms had a 0 to 10 integer response scale.

The methods used to measure participant age varied from case study to case study, with some participants asking for exact age, but most using age ranges, which varied between case studies. These were made compatible by setting the age to the range mid-point. A gender response was prompted by a single word “Gender”, with response options including “Male”, “Female”, “Non-binary”, “Other”, and “Prefer not to say”. “Other” was never answered and “Prefer not to say” was treated as missing data. The mismatch between gender-related and sex-related vocabulary was present in the English original. Economic situation was measured with the item “How do you rate your own economic situation?” with response options “Very good” (coded as 5), “Good” (4), “Partly good/partly bad” (3), “Bad” (2), “Very bad” (1), and “Prefer not to say” (missing). Education was measured with the item “What is the highest educational level that you have attained?”, with response options “No formal education” (1), “Primary school” (2), “Secondary school technical/vocational type” (3), “Complete secondary school: university preparatory type” (4), “Some university-level education, without degree” (5), “University-level education, with degree” (6), “PhD or equivalent” (8). Numeric codes are those found in data files.

1.3 Analysis details

1.3.1 Approach

All analyses are conducted with R. All data and analysis scripts (including R Markdown showing results) can be downloaded from our GitHub repository (Anon, 2026), which will be preserved with a snapshot on Zenodo following acceptance of the manuscript.

1.3.2 Data preparation

Participants were included in the analyses if they provided complete data for at least one of the two primary attitude measures (ESI or WTS). Complete case requirements were present data for the attitude variable and the perceived norm variable.

1.3.3 Variable computation

For each stakeholder group within each case study, we computed Environmental Pluralistic Ignorance (EPI) scores for individuals as follows:

1. The actual proportion of individuals who agreed with the attitude (scored ≥ 4 on the 5-point scale), converted to a percentage (same value for all individuals within the group)
2. The perceived norm (what percentage of others that respondents believed agreed), based on responses to a 0–10 scale converted to percentages
3. The EPI score is the actual percentage minus the perceived norm percentage

We computed both agreement-based EPI scores (for testing H1) and disagreement-based EPI scores (for testing H2), where disagreement was defined as scores ≤ 2 on the 5-point scale.

For ordinal regression models, all continuous predictors (perceived norms and, where applicable, an attitude score) were standardized (mean-centred and scaled to unit variance) within the complete case dataset.

1.3.4 Variable descriptions across case studies

Where variables are described with percentages, for example mean percentage agreeing with items, or mean percentage participants estimated would agree, these are grand means of case study means, with no weighting.

1.3.5 Reliability analysis

We assessed reliability for both attitude measures using Pearson correlations between the two items administered for each construct, using all cases complete for the two items. For ESI, we correlated `envCit1` (“Acting environmentally friendly is an important part of who I am”) with `envCit2` (“I see myself as an environmentally friendly person”) ($n = 333$). For WTS, we correlated `willToSac1` (“I would be willing to accept cuts in my standard of living to protect the environment”) with `willToSac2` (“I would be willing to pay much higher taxes in order to protect the environment”) ($n = 230$).

1.3.6 Permutation sign tests for pluralistic ignorance (H1 and H2)

We tested whether EPI scores differed significantly from zero using permutation-based sign tests (Oehlert, 2023). The test procedure:

1. Calculate the observed mean EPI score
2. Generate 99,999 random permutations by randomly multiplying each observation by +1 or -1
3. Calculate the mean for each permutation
4. To generate a two-sided test, compute the p -value as the proportion of permuted absolute means that equal or exceed the observed absolute mean

1.3.7 Parametric bootstrap for proportion of case studies with positive EPI

To quantify uncertainty in the proportion of case studies showing positive pluralistic ignorance (i.e., positive EPI scores), we conducted parametric bootstrap analyses for both ESI and WTS. This analysis addresses the question: across how many case studies, in the population of which these case studies are representative, do we expect to observe a positive pluralistic ignorance score? When the quantity of interest is a function of both fixed effects and random effects in a mixed model, parametric bootstrap is an appropriate resampling method (Austin & Leckie, 2020). The models have EPI scores as the outcome, stakeholder category as a fixed effect, and random intercepts for case study. They were fitted using the `lmer()` function from the `lme4` package (Bates et al., 2015). For each attitude (ESI and WTS), we performed parametric bootstrap resampling with 99,999

104 iterations using the `bootMer()` function. Parametric bootstrapping simulates new datasets from the fitted
105 model by:

- 106 1. Drawing new random effects from their estimated distribution
- 107 2. Drawing new residuals from their estimated distribution
- 108 3. Constructing simulated response values based on the model structure
- 109 4. Refitting the model to each simulated dataset

110 For each bootstrap iteration, we calculated the expected proportion of case studies that would show positive
111 EPI scores. This was computed by:

- 112 1. Extracting the mean fixed effect prediction for each case study
- 113 2. For each case study, calculating the probability that a random intercept drawn from the estimated
114 random effects distribution, when added to the fixed effect, would yield a positive value (using the
115 normal CDF with the estimated standard deviation of random intercepts)
- 116 3. Averaging these probabilities across all case studies to obtain the expected proportion

117 This quantity represents the expected proportion of case studies where pluralistic ignorance would be present,
118 accounting for uncertainty in the random effects. We calculated 95% confidence intervals for this proportion
119 using the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of the bootstrap distribution. We report the point estimate calculated
120 from the original fitted model; the bootstrapped means showed little bias.

121 **1.3.8 Ordinal regression models for the associations between personal and perceived attitudes** 122 **(H3 and beyond)**

123 We used cumulative link models to examine whether perceived norms predicted individual attitudes while
124 accounting for stakeholder category and case study. For both ESI and WTS, we fit a series of five models with
125 increasing complexity:

126 **Model 1:** $\text{attitude} \sim \text{perceived norm}$

- 127 • Basic model with perceived norm as the sole predictor

128 **Model 2:** $\text{attitude} \sim \text{perceived norm} + \text{stakeholder category}$

- 129 • Adds stakeholder category as a fixed effect (the reference category is the stakeholder group with the
130 largest sample size for that outcome)

131 **Model 3:** $\text{attitude} \sim \text{perceived norm} + \text{stakeholder category} + (1 | \text{case study})$

- 132 • Adds random intercepts for case study

133 **Model 4:** $\text{attitude} \sim \text{perceived norm} + \text{stakeholder category} + (1 | \text{case study}) + \text{perceived norm} : \text{stakeholder}$
134 category

- 135 • Adds interaction between perceived norm and stakeholder category, allowing the norm-attitude re-
136 lationship to vary across stakeholder categories

137 **Model 5:** $\text{attitude} \sim \text{perceived norm} + \text{stakeholder category} + (1 | \text{case study}) + (0 + \text{perceived norm} | \text{case}$
138 $\text{study})$

- 139 • Replaces the stakeholder category interaction with random slopes for perceived norm by case study,
140 allowing the norm-attitude relationship to vary across sites

141 Models were fitted using the cumulative link mixed model framework with a logit link function (proportional
142 odds model). For Models 1 and 2 (fixed effects only), we used the `clm()` function from the ordinal package in

143 R (Christensen, 2025). For Models 3–5 (including random effects), we used `clmm()` with Laplace approxima-
144 tion. The proportional odds assumption was tested by applying the `nominal_test()` function to Model 1.

145 For each model, we report regression coefficients for the perceived norm predictor converted to odds ratios
146 through exponentiation, and 95% confidence intervals obtained from the profile method (Venzon &
147 Moolgavkar, 1988).

148 **1.3.9 Cross-attitude model**

149 We fit an additional model to examine whether how ESI and perceived WTS norms independently predicted
150 WTS, which was as WTS Model 3 with the addition of ESI (which was treated as numeric and standardised):

151 **Model 6:** $WTS \sim WTS \text{ perceived norm} + ESI + \text{stakeholder category} + (1 | \text{case study})$

152 **1.4 Presentation of ordinal regressions (in violation of preregistration)**

153 The preregistered modelling approach was to begin with linear regression, progress to ordinal regression if
154 inspection of residual plots indicated poor fit, and progress to beta regression if the proportional odds assump-
155 tion of ordinal regression was violated. The linear models did fit badly, especially for ESI because of heavy
156 skew (see primary analysis R Markup file). There was no evidence the ordinal model for ESI violated the pro-
157 portional odds assumption, $p = .066$, but the ordinal model for WTS showed a minor violation, $p = .013$.
158 Following the preregistered procedure, we therefore progressed to beta regression (specific method docu-
159 mented by the beta regression R Markup file) and obtained the same pattern of results (in terms of statistical
160 significance and direction of effect) as using the ordinal models.

161 The reasons we violate the preregistration by presenting the ordinal models rather than the beta regression
162 models are as follows. Firstly, as stated by Harrell (2020), in his article “Violation of Proportional Odds is Not
163 Fatal”, “Many researchers worry about violations of the [proportional odds assumption] Besides the fact
164 that this frequently makes them turn to a much worse approach, the harm done by violations of the propor-
165 tional odds assumption usually do not prevent the proportional odds model from providing a reasonable treat-
166 ment effect assessment.” Secondly, although beta regression can sometimes be used for Likert items, it is not
167 designed for ordinal scales, but rather proportions (so we risk the mistake Harrell cautions against). Thirdly,
168 the regression coefficients of ordinal regressions are more easily interpreted (as odds ratios). Fourthly, essen-
169 tially the same results are obtained by both methods. Finally, we were not aware of these issues at the point of
170 preregistration so had not taken them into account.

171 **1.5 Ethics statement**

172 The central PRO-COAST team (1) provided research ethics training for each partner (important as some
173 partners are not academic organisations), (2) informed each partner that they should follow relevant local eth-
174 ical regulations when collecting data, and that they should obtain informed consent from participants, and
175 (3) maintains on file signed declarations from partners attesting that they have done this.

176 **1.6 Use of AI statement**

177 LLM was used to assist with writing of analysis code. The authors have manually checked all LLM generated
178 code and take responsibility for it. Large Language Models (LLM) were not used to generate natural language
179 (with one exception) but were sometimes used to check style. The single exception is that the first draft of
180 section 1.3 (Analysis details) in this document was generated by LLM summarisation of the relevant R code.
181 This was dual purpose as a time-saving exercise and to further check the code. The LLM-generated text was
182 carefully checked and extensively modified.

2 Analysis results

2.1 H2: Pluralistic ignorance concerning disagreement rather than agreement with target items

The pre-registered hypotheses included a converse of H1, that participants would also show pluralistic ignorance but concerning the percentage of those who disagreed rather than agreed with the target Likert items. Because this hypothesis is somewhat trivial, as it mirrors H1, we present results here in Supplementary Materials. We note, however, that it is not entirely trivial, because it would be possible for there to be pluralistic ignorance for agreement, but not disagreement, if participants guessed that large numbers of people took a neutral stance on the items.

In fact, pluralistic ignorance for disagreement is also clear. The mean percentage (across cross studies) of participants who disagreed with the ESI item (“Acting environmentally friendly is an important part of who I am”) was 4%, whereas the mean percentage (across case studies) that participants guessed would disagree was 37%. For the WTS item (“I would be willing to accept cuts in my standard of living to protect the environment”), 21% disagreed, whereas the mean percentage they guessed would disagree was 43%. The same type of permutation sign-test as used for H1 revealed these were significant differences, both p -values < .001.

2.2 Precise values for the numbers illustrated by Figure 1

Tables S1 and S2 illustrate precise values for the numbers illustrated by Figure 1, for ESI (environmentalist self-identity) and WTS (willingness to sacrifice for the environment) respectively.

Table S2

Precise values for the numbers illustrated by Figure 1, left panel, environmentalist self-identity (ESI)

Case study	Stakeholder category	Percent who agree	Percent estimated to agree	<i>n</i>
Malta	Commercial	100%	33%	6
Malta	Tourists	96%	62%	73
Malta	Government	87%	63%	15
Norway	Wild resource users	80%	59%	30
Norway	Environment protectors	95%	76%	21
Estonia	Local community	80%	53%	10
UK	Wild resource users	100%	67%	20
UK	Local community	73%	56%	15
UK	Environment protectors	100%	88%	3
Slovenia	Local community	85%	62%	59
Slovenia	Commercial	44%	68%	9
Slovenia	Environment protectors	100%	77%	3
Ireland	Government	83%	38%	6
Ireland	Commercial	83%	22%	6
Italy	Local community	100%	73%	26
Italy	Environment protectors	100%	77%	7

Table S3*Precise values for the numbers illustrated by Figure 1, right panel, willingness to sacrifice (WTS)*

Case study	Stakeholder category	Percent who agree	Percent estimated to agree	<i>n</i>
Malta	Commercial	50%	15%	6
Malta	Tourists	71%	34%	72
Malta	Government	79%	44%	14
Norway	Wild resource users	65%	33%	31
Norway	Environment protectors	76%	54%	21
Romania	Tourists	33%	35%	12
Romania	Government	67%	33%	3
UK	Wild resource users	75%	41%	20
UK	Local community	56%	33%	16
UK	Environment protectors	100%	75%	3
Ireland	Government	17%	15%	6
Ireland	Commercial	33%	18%	6

3 Additional survey for Arne case study

As this survey was on a small scale and does not merit separate publication, we include a full description of it here. In 2025, approximately 550 leaflets were delivered to household letterboxes in Arne Parish, UK, to invite residents to attend a local community event at the parish hall. The leaflets introduced ongoing local work as part of the PRO-COAST project, stating as the objective that “a community-led trial is underway to study squirrel populations and assess the potential for reintroducing red squirrels in the future.” The leaflet did not mention that culling grey squirrels is necessary to reintroduce red squirrels (Schuchert et al., 2014), but it did mention that grey squirrels damage trees and spread a fatal disease to red squirrels.

Between 40 and 50 residents attended the meeting. Upon arrival, attendees were invited to complete a paper questionnaire (which included some questions not addressed here). A total of 28 questionnaires were completed. The target attitude question asked, “Would you support proposals to kill grey squirrels locally to make it possible to establish red squirrels?” with a five-point response scale from “No, strongly oppose” (1) to “Yes, strongly support” (5). The perceived norm question followed immediately, and asked, “Consider other people at the meeting today. Out of 10 such people, how many do you guess would answer ‘Yes’ to the previous question (support proposals to kill greys to make it possible to establish reds)?”, with a numeric response scale between 0 and 10. There was no missing data for these questions from respondents.

The level of support was 82%, whereas the perceived level of support was 51%, $p < .001$, permutation sign test with 99,999 samples (Oehlert, 2023). The two variables correlated, $r = .41$, $p = .031$.

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